

Role of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Business Organisations

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M. Dhilip Kumar.

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D.Jeyaraman

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Aditanar College of Arts and Science Tiruchendur

M.Dhilip Kumar

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Aditanar College of Arts and Science Tiruchendur

Abstract

In the recent years Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has viewed incredible increase in awareness and control in the universal area. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) denotes the strategies that business organizations employ to conduct their business in a way that is ethical, society friendly and advantageous to public in terms of development. It is an idea where Business organizations apart from their profitability and development show concentration in social and environmental well-being by taking the accountability of impact of their activities on investors, personnel, stakeholders, customers, suppliers, and civil society. In this paper the scope of CSR was analyzed under the three-broad point of view viz., 1. Economic point of view; 2. Social point of view; and 3. Environmental point of view. Further in this paper the scope of Corporate Social Responsibility were also presented.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR, business organisations, social, environmental, Society.

Introduction

In the recent years Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has viewed incredible increase in awareness and control in the universal arena. CSR that developed in the year 1960 was an effort to link business organisations with society. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) denotes the strategies that business organisations employ to conduct their business in a way that is ethical, society friendly and advantageous to public in terms of development. It is an idea where Business organizations apart from their profitability and development show concentration in social and environmental well-being by taking the accountability of impact of their activities on investors, personnel, stakeholders, customers, suppliers, and civil society. It takes into attention the social and environmental implications of business financial decisions.

Scope of Corporate Social Responsibility

The scope of Corporate Social Responsibility was analyzed under the three-broad point of view viz., 1. Economic point of view; 2. Social point of view; and 3. Environmental point of view.

1. Economic Point of View: The economic point of view of CSR comprise of understanding the economic effects of the company's existence. The economic side of the sustainability agenda should rather consider the direct and indirect economic effects that the business organization's operations have on the adjacent community and on the company's stakeholders. That is to say what makes up corporate economic responsibility.

2. Social Point of View: Numerous business organizations are becoming progressively active in addressing social concerns. Social responsibility means being responsible for the social effects the business organisations has on people even indirectly. This comprises the people within the business organisation, in the supply chain of the business organisation, in the community the business organisation is in and as customers of the business organisation which means the whole lot of stakeholder. It denotes to the organization's obligation to make choices and take actions that will contribute to the well fare and interests of society as well as those of the organization.

3. Environmental Point of View: Environmental concern and justifiable growth are a vital support of the corporate social responsibility. Environmental and ecological problems have been an important topic of discussion over the years in the business world. The information and problems within the dimensions have developed across a countryside of changing business realities. The environmental impact of business was first realized during the year 1970.

Role of corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility plays very important role in smooth operational of business organizations.

- Built-up strong Customer Relations: Business organisations must prove themselves to customers to build long-term, trusting relationships through corporate social responsibility. Business organisations must also get involved in the community to give back. This community connection helps your business organisation to the local markets in which you function.
- Develop morale among Employees towards business organisation: Employees are a business organization's greatest valued asset. This is the premise of a business organization's responsibility to this vital stakeholder group with regard to Corporate Social Responsibility obedience. This means treating employees with respect and offering impartial working conditions. It also establishing impartial hiring practices and encouraging a non-discriminatory work environment. This progresses morale within the work environment and boosts teamwork.
- Increase Business Organisations Profitability and Worth: A Corporate Social Responsibility strategy increases business organisations overall profitability and worth. The introduction of energy competences and waste reutilizing cuts operative costs and aids the environment. Corporate Social Responsibility also rises business organisations accountability and its transparency with investment specialists and the media, shareholders and local people. This in turn improves its reputation amongst investors. The effect is a worthy circle where the business organisations stock value increases and its access to investment capital is improved.
- Show a Factual Commitment: The most fruitful corporate social responsibility programs assimilate Corporate Social Responsibility together to display a factual commitment to a cause. If a business organisation that practices sustainable resources in their goods, donates financial resources to environmental causes, and permits employees on duty for volunteering at environmental activities would be showing a factual commitment to the environment that goes beyond any single Corporate Social Responsibility initiative.

- **Popularity in Social Media** One of the motives that business organisation should have noticeable Corporate Social Responsibility movements is due to the importance and prevalence of social media. Business organisation that want to protect their image understand that social media is an important fragment of public perception. When a business organisation workouts social responsibility in the method of fund mobilizing using social media to promote these actions helps to create a positive image and it is a great way to engage with your audience on a deeper level that goes beyond your goods and services.
- **Community Relationship:** Community relationship shaping consumer perception and building a business organization's image. Business organisations that actively promote their social responsibility actions often take steps to expose these efforts through the media. Receiving the word out about donations, employee volunteer programs, and other corporate social responsibility initiatives is a powerful image building instrument that can build publicity for the business organisations in both online and offline media.
- **Strong Relationship with Government:** Business organisations that place an emphasis on corporate social responsibility naturally have a relaxed experience when dealing with government regulators. In contrast, businesses organisations that present a reckless disrespect for social responsibility tend to find themselves fending off various inquiries and probes. The more optimistic the community perception is that a business organisation takes social responsibility extremely; the less likely it is that activist groups will launch public movements and demand government inquiries against it.
- **Developing an Optimistic Workplace Atmosphere:** Lastly, one of the chief benefits of encouraging social responsibility in the workplace is the optimistic atmosphere you build for your personnel. When workforces and management feel they are working for a business organisation that has a true morality, they will likely be more passionate and engaged in their works. This can build a sense of community and solidarity which brings everyone composed and leads to more contented, more productive workforces.

Conclusion

Corporate Social Responsibility denoting to way that business organisations are managed to bring about an overall optimistic impression on the peoples, cultures, societies and environments in which they function. The scope of Corporate Social Responsibility was analyzed under the three-broad point of view viz., 1. Economic point of view; 2. Social point of view; and 3. Environmental point of view. Corporate Social Responsibility plays very important role in smooth operational of business organizations. CSR built strong customer relations, develop morale among employees towards business organisation and increase business organisations profitability and worth.

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